

Although reaching the limits of physics, silicon technology continues to improve, therefore still allowing the design of improved and better performing circuits and systems.

Silicon technology is still in the game

By CARLO REITA, SANDRINE CHERAMY and MARC DURANTON

Silicon technology, which has fuelled the improvement of ICT system performance for the last sixty years* or more, is reaching the limits of physics, with device size in the range of a few tens of atoms. However, even if the scaling itself reaches its limit (3nm is announced for 2022), various approaches (new geometry, new materials, 3D stacking, ...) allow for further improvement of the density and efficiency of transistors, allowing chips that are more efficient and complex to be designed.

Key insights

- Silicon technology is still finding new approaches to increase its performance.
- New transistor structures are emerging, such as Gate All Around FET (GaaFET).
- 3D structures reduce the length of wires (and therefore power dissipation) and increase the density of systems when compared to traditional packaging technologies.
- The use of interposer and chiplet technology will allow a reduction in design costs (thanks to the possible re-use of IP and to smaller computing devices) and the mixing of different technologies, such as analog, power converters and digital.

Key recommendations

- Continue investigating new approaches to further increase performance of silicon-based systems.
- Europe should keep hold of its knowhow in this domain, otherwise it will risk losing the ability to make optimal use of those new technologies.
- The use of interposer and chiplet technology might become the sweet spot for edge devices, having the best performance/cost ratio.

The semiconductor technology CMOS, which fuels the digital era, has reached a period of diminishing return, and will require gigantic investment to allow further improvement to its performance. At the same time, no other technology is on the horizon as a possible replacement, at least for the foreseeable future. However, performance is still improving, albeit more slowly, with new designs, in a “3nm” technology, scheduled for the latter half of 2022. This article will explain what the reality of scaling is and the various solutions that are used to continue improvements in performance, at least for the next five years.

3nm available in volume production in 2022

“In August 2020, TSMC announced details of its N3 3nm process, which is new rather than being an improvement over its N5 5nm process [7]. Compared with the N5 process, the N3 process should offer a 10–15% (1.10–1.15×) increase in performance, or a 25–35% (1.25–1.35×) decrease in power consumption, with a 1.7× increase in logic density (a scaling factor of 0.58), a 20% increase (0.8 scaling factor) in SRAM cell density, and a 10% increase in analog circuitry density. Since many designs include considerably more SRAM than logic, (a common ratio being 70% SRAM to 30% logic) die shrinks are expected to only be of around 26%. TSMC plans risk production in 2021 with volume production in the second half of 2022” [8].

* The first working example of an integrated circuit was demonstrated by Jack Kilby on 12 September 1958.

The reality of scaling

News of the impending end of the microelectronics scaling roadmap has reached even the general public, but as usual, the situation is more complex than what it appears to be at first glance. The attention of the press, following Intel's longstanding lead in microelectronics, has mostly focused on Moore's law. This "law" was, in reality, an observation made by G. Moore [1], when still based at Fairchild and before the CMOS devices technology was even in production. He observed that the density of the components on a chip had been doubling roughly every year; in 1975 a more complete version of the paper postulated the doubling as being every three years [2]. This statement is more a business model than a law, and the only real law derived from the physics of the MOS transistors was outlined R. Dennard in 1974. This law states the relations between number of physical characteristics when a uniform reduction of dimension is applied to a standard MOS transistor, notably the power density (that remains constant) and the speed (Figure 2). In fact, the improvements resulting from the shrinking of dimensions had already slowed down or disappeared altogether by around 2005. In his paper, R. Dennard had indicated where this type of purely geometrical scaling would start breaking down: the dopant concentration. In fact, the behaviour of electrical junctions is controlled by the dopant concentration in silicon and this cannot physically be larger than a few percent of the atomic density of Si. This limit is reached at around 20nm to 30nm of gate length. Two other limitations of pure geometrical scaling were always very clear: dissipation and patterning.

The power dissipation per unit area of the transistor is constant, so, at some point, the increase of transistor numbers per unit area of chip would make it impossible to extract the dissipated heat. Dissipation is directly proportional to frequency of operation and inversely proportional to the square of the supply voltage. As a consequence, the speed at which the transistor can be operated has to be limited (hence the stop at around 2-4GHz for the processor clocks) and not all the transistors may be operating at the same time (parts

Figure 1: 48 years of microprocessor trend [6]

THE PHYSICS OF SCALING: DENNARD'S LAW

Device or Circuit Parameter	Scaling Factor
Device dimension t_{ox}, L, W	$1/\kappa$
Doping concentration N_a	κ
Voltage V	$1/\kappa$
Current I	$1/\kappa$
Capacitance $\epsilon A/t$	$1/\kappa$
Delay time/circuit VC/I	$1/\kappa$
Power dissipation/circuit VI	$1/\kappa^2$
Power density VI/A	1

R. Dennard et al., IEEE JSSC, 1974

- **Scaling improve performance!**

Figure 2 Dennard's scaling law

of circuits need to be switched off from time to time, also called "dark silicon"). The supply voltage has also been reduced but there is a limit at which the transistor cannot be controlled (around 0.3V).

The second limitation has always been the way patterning can be done. The optical process of transferring the image onto the layer to be patterned is limited by the wavelength. Initially this limitation was reduced by the introduction of powerful lasers down to 248nm, which was sufficient until the normal scaling broke down.

The push for the reduction of size, then, has continued in order to keep reducing

the unit cost of the chips but the era of pure geometrical shrinking has now been over for more than ten years. The continuation of the shrinking of dimensions has led to the need for some major changes in the structure of the devices and hence a major complexification. To control the junction after the maximum dopant density was reached, the devices needed to be fabricated on thin layers of silicon and this brought about the FinFET and the FDSOI (Fully Depleted Silicon on Insulator) technologies. The reduction of the dimension and this confinement entail a reduction of the maximum current density in the transistor channel limiting the capacity of driving the metallic interconnects and effectively the

speed. To overcome this limitation, strained layers and silicon germanium alloys have been introduced to present higher current mobilities. In order to limit the leakage from the control gate, thicker, high permittivity oxides have been introduced by first adding hafnium to silicon dioxide and/or using pure hafnium oxide.

The issue of patterning has always been central and, early on, the lithography tools have standardized on a reduction by 4X of the mask pattern projected down to the photoresist coated wafers. The way to improve resolution has relied on improving the two parameters determining resolution of an optical system: numerical aperture NA and wavelength λ . From classical optics, in fact, is well known that the minimum pitch for two lines to be imaged is directly proportional to λ and inversely proportional to the NA (diffraction limit). The wavelength, hence, has been progressively reduced from 365nm down to 193nm while NA has increased progressively to 0.95. At this point (early 2000s), the first attempt to further reduce the wavelength failed (157nm did not pass the research stage) and so, like in the microscopes of the late 1800s, to further improve the resolution a higher refraction index medium was introduced between the last lens and the wafer. These systems, using 193nm laser illumination, are known as immersion systems and have supported the scaling down to 20nm node. At the same time research started on a radical change of wavelength to move to 13.5nm (Extreme UV, EUV) requiring the imaging process to be done in a vacuum and using only mirrors in the optical system. Unfortunately, the ten years initially forecast for the development of such tools became nearly twenty years and the industry had to find other ways to keep the scaling pace. Initially, modifications of patterns on the mask were applied to correct proximity effects (Optical Proximity Correction, OPC, techniques), but soon another optic “trick” was used. By imaging only along one axis and accepting a deterioration on the perpendicular one while also adapting the illumination source, it is possible to reduce the pitch below the classical limit. This has led to radically new design constraints forcing superposition of layers with opposite directions leading to

Figure 3: The design parameters of a logic gate

the fact that the density of a process node can be related to the pitch of the three critical layers (gate, contact and metal). When the limits of even this technique were reached, the patterns of each layer were separated into multiple masks with multiple intermeshing exposures needed to attain reduced pitches. These techniques go by the name of “multiple patterning” and have dramatically increased production and design costs. However, at the 7nm node, the EUV tools have finally become available, simplifying somehow the designs at the cost of other specific issues but providing once more the real possibility of imaging at the dimensions required for the 5nm and 3nm nodes.

Collectively the use of all these techniques has allowed what has been called “equivalent scaling”, meaning that the density has kept increasing even if the dimension of the transistors themselves has not been reduced as in the past.

Essentially, at each generation, the gate length is not scaled by a factor 0.7 to obtain a gain by a factor of two in surface for the device as was seen in the past; the gain is now only around 20%-30%. Performance is typically improved by between 20% and 40% at each node as a result of this reduction and of multiple new technology developments like the previously mentioned new materials, use of strain, change in shape and aspect ratio of devices, etc. The density of devices, however, still tends to

improve by a factor of two by reducing tolerances (thanks to better lithography and processes in general) and playing on the layout (number of fins per transistor, number of tracks per cell, number and position of contacts). The use of these techniques introduces a level of confusion and uncertainty about how to compare technologies and processes between nodes and across manufacturers and applications (e.g. very large differences in densities between logic, high performance, low power and analog libraries for a given node).

The naming convention for the “equivalent scaling” has also started to be a misleading one. In effect, until the 45-40nm the value which indicated the node (here 40nm) was typically the gate length of the smallest devices or half of the pitch of the densest interconnect metal layer. Pioneered by Intel (moving the naming from 28nm to 22nm ...) with the marketing department of all players following suit, the node naming stopped reflecting any real physical dimension (e.g. at 7nm the smallest physical dimension of any parameter is ~ 12 nm ...) and became just a commercial label. In Figure 4 are some examples of node naming by manufacturers and real dimensions in the design and devices. Where a reference is not provided, data is extrapolated from multiple sources. Real data for 5nm and 3nm exists publicly but only in the form of company announcements and so has not been included.

SILICON TECHNOLOGY IS STILL IN THE GAME

Nominal node		28nm	22nm	20nm	18nm	16nm	14nm	12nm	10nm	7nm	5nm	3nm	2nm (N2 imec estimation)
Intel	Lg (nm)		24				20		16	~14nm			10nm
	Fin Pitch (nm)		60 FinFET				FinFET 42		FinFET 34	FinFET			16
	CPP (nm)		90				70		54	47			42
	M1 (nm)		80				64		44	26			16
	SRAM		HD 0.092µm ²				0.0588µm ²		0.0312µm ²	0.027µm ²			
	Year Publication		VLSI 2012				IEDM 2014		IEDM 2017/ISSCC2018				
Risk Prod		2011				2014		1Q18		1H2021			
Samsung	Lg (nm)	32		25	25		30		~20	~16		~16	~13
	Fin Pitch (nm)	BULK		BULK	FDSOI		48 FinFET		Single Fin 42	FinFET 7LPP	FinFET 5LPE	Horizontal Nanosheets (HNS)	
	CPP (nm)	114		86	86		78		68	54/57	54/57	40	
	M1 (nm)	90		64	64		64		51	36	36	32	
	SRAM	0.152µm ²		0.084µm ²			0.064/0.08µm ²		0.04µm ²	HD 6T SRAM 0.026µm ²			
	Year Publication	ICSIST 2011		VLSI 2012			JSSC 2014		ISSCC/VLSI 2017	VLSI 2017/ISSCC2017-2018			
Risk Prod	2011		2013			4Q-2015		1Q2017		1H-19	2H2020		
TSMC	Lg (nm)	30	30	30			33		25	25	18	16	~13
	Fin Pitch (nm)	BULK	BULK	BULK			FinFET 45		FinFET 45	FinFET	FinFET 7FF	FinFET N5	Horizontal Nanowire (HNW)
	CPP (nm)	118	105	90			90/80		90/80	64	54	50	45
	M1 (nm)	90	80	64			64		64	42	40	28	22
	SRAM	0.155µm ²	0.15µm ²				0.07µm ²			0.03µm ²	0.027µm ²		0.021µm ²
	Year Publication	VLSI 2012	VLSI 2012	VLSI 2014			IEDM 2013		6Track	VLSI 2016	IEDM 2016		ISSC 2020
Risk Prod	2011	2018	2019			4Q-2015		3Q2016	4Q2016	3Q-17		1H2020	
GF	Lg (nm)						30						
	Fin Pitch (nm)						48 Fin FET						
	CPP (nm)						78						
	M1 (nm)						67						
	SRAM						0.110µm ²						
	Year Publication						IEDM 2016						
Risk Prod						2H-2016							
SMIC	Lg (nm)	30					30						
	Fin Pitch (nm)	BULK					48 Fin FET						
	CPP (nm)	118					78						
	M1 (nm)	90					67						
	SRAM												
	Year Publication												
Risk Prod	2016						2019						
Forecast													

Figure 4: comparison of the technologies of various foundries

While during the last sixty years of microelectronics development it has been unclear which technical solutions would drive development ten years down the line, there was never any doubt that there was no fundamental technical limitation and that competition guaranteed that the necessary investments were made in a timely way. What is more, R&D activity provided a number of options with a degree of maturity that was instilled confidence that they would be ready when needed. Over the last ten years the situation has changed dramatically. Technically the specification for the 3nm node is very close to the physical limit for transport in semiconductors (gate length of 7 to 10nm) before stochastic phenomena introduce an intolerable degree of variability. No investigations carried out by R&D groups have found materials or device architectures that have the potential to behave better than silicon [3].

Around these dimensions, the device structures need a major new modification to keep the gate controlling the current flow effectively. Both FinFET (impossible to reduce the fin thickness for structural reasons) and FDSOI (not enough current per channel) need to move to horizontally stacked nanowires and nanosheets. In fact, this type of new structure will have the technology converge again as it can be seen as an evolution of FinFET where the fin is split in multiple layers or a series of FDSOI channels on top of each other. These, announced by Samsung and demonstrated in the past both by IBM and CEA-LETI [4], are really at the limit of what can be obtained in term of scaling of individual components [5]. Nothing better has been shown in literature in the last ten years and so we may well have to start looking more for further improvements in the other parts of systems such as in the assembly of multi-

ple chips, management of the I/O, packaging, etc.

The introduction of production capable EUV tools, the delay in the deployment of which generated doubts about the feasibility of the scaling, has slowed down the increase in cost and has given a greater degree of freedom to the process, making the new device structure manufacturable. The road towards 2nm node (10nm gate length) 3D devices, while not free from risk, now looks viable. The target of such devices being in production in 2024 is a reasonable one and so the gain in density and performance should continue at the same rate as that of the last five years.

All the above is applicable to logic devices. Where memories are concerned, the very high regularity of their structure, both for Dynamic Random Access Memory (DRAM) or NAND Flash memory, has allowed a path that has been somewhat smoother but where the use of the third dimension has occurred earlier. This has happened as a result of two requirements: density improvement in the chip and very large throughput for the I/O. Some of the logic processes are being progressively introduced into the memory (the latest is the use of replacement metal gates in 3D

Figure 5: Evolution of the transistors' topology (from <https://tellitlikeitisnews.com/samsung-announces-3nm-gaa-mbcfet-pdk-version-0-1/>)

NAND) when necessary. Some of the typical memory 3D techniques will progressively filter back towards logic integration at the same time. In the case of memories devices too, then, there does not appear to be any real bottleneck in their continuous improvement for the next five years. In fact, the large amount of memory required in AI-dedicated circuits will probably drive them even harder towards higher densities and speed, with SSD disks increasingly competitive with mechanical hard disks.

Figure 6: Benefits of 3DVLSI (Source: CEA-LETI)

Figure 7: View of different advanced packaging solutions for high-end applications. (Source: Yole, 3DTSV & 2,5D 2016 report)

Figure 8: 3D parallel and 3D sequential positioning, depending on partitioning granularity and pitch of interconnect (Source: CEA-LETI)

Playing with 3D

3D-stacking is a promising new technology that will allow the density of transistors in systems to continue increasing by using the third dimension to stack dies of silicon one above another even if the transistors do not shrink any further. This technology is already in use for some specific products but needs to be more widely developed to enable greater diversity of chips at an acceptable cost.

Some of the key advantages of heterogeneous integration compared to classical planar architecture are:

- Transistors, or function by surface unit increase;
- Possible re-use of advanced intellectual property (IP), which allows faster time-to-market as well as cost reduction;
- The ability to mix chips with the most appropriate technology for each given function.

The first objective of heterogeneous integration, in this context, is to maintain or increase the energy efficiency of the global system while reducing its size. Several solutions are already available in foundries or outsourced semiconductor assembly and test providers, mainly driven by TSMC with their integrated fan-out (InFO) and CoWoS advanced packaging, or Intel with its EMIB and FOREVOS solutions.

Nevertheless, current solutions will soon face seriously challenges in terms of achieving high density of interconnects between separate functions (like those required by logic to memory) while achieving a dissipation of less than 1pJ/bit per vertical link.

This figure of merit naturally leads to two different but complementary integrations: 3DIC stack (also called 3D parallel) and 3D monolithic (also called 3D sequential). Here also, the technology will be chosen with regard to the architecture and the density required, as shown in Figure 8.

3DIC stack

3DIC stack with through-silicon via (TSV) and μbumps are well known, mainly for field-programmable gate array (FPGA) applications (partitioned dies on a passive

Figure 9: One possible architecture partitioning between chiplets and interposer (Source: Leti)

Figure 10: A future system might contain a CPU chiplet and several GPUs all attached to the same piece of network-enabled silicon (Source: AMD)

Figure 11: Zen Based EPYC Processors (Source: The Next Platform)

Figure 12: Apple M1 system in package

silicon interposer), and for high-bandwidth memory (HBM) and hybrid memory cube (HMC) stacking. The pitch between 3D features is in the range of $40\mu\text{m}$, while a pitch of less than $10\mu\text{m}$ is evaluated to reach $<1\text{pJ/bit}$ for the consumption of each vertical link.

That's the reason why advanced 3D technology with very small TSV (a diameter in the range of the μm) and very fine-pitch chip-to-chip interconnects is required. The chip-to-chip fine-pitch interconnect may be based on the μbumps (copper and solder) interconnect or direct hybrid bonding. Wafer-to-wafer by direct hybrid bonding is also a potential solution, already famous for CMOS image sensor (CIS), by partitioning the sensing layer from the logic layer, and more recently by embedding in the stack a third layer with dynamic random access memory (DRAM).

As an example, DARPA's Common Heterogeneous Integration and IP Reuse Strategies (CHIPS) programme demonstrates work in this area, while AMD, INTEL and CEA-LETI have published work and launched initiatives for advanced silicon interposers and chiplets.

In several application domains, advanced 3D integration may advantageously replace a multi-core monolithic planar die.

A further advantage of die stacking is the innovative potential it provides to introduce novel materials, such as III-V chemical compounds like gallium nitride (GaN), onto silicon CMOS wafers. This is another example of "using the right technology and the right material for the right function". Additionally, this would save some rare or expensive materials by limiting their use.

The roadmap of alignment accuracy is already quite clear with the objective of reaching under $10\mu\text{m}$ of pitch having already been achieved and advanced proofs-of-concept from laboratories having delivered a $1\mu\text{m}$ pitch for wafer-to-wafer hybrid bonding (CEA-LETI, 2017), or $3\mu\text{m}$ for a μbumps interconnect (Imec, 2017).

On the industrial side, the AMD "Rome" Epyc processors use this principle: all of the

Figure 13: According to Anandtech [9] "Whilst in the past 5 years Intel has managed to increase their best single-thread performance by about 28%, Apple has managed to improve their designs by 198%, or 2.98x (let's call it 3x) the performance of the Apple A9 of late 2015".

I/O and memory controllers are set into a 14nm "interposer" that sits at the centre of the Rome package. The compute chiplets are 7nm.

The Apple M1, designed with TSMC 5nm technology, uses a similar approach, with the main core and the memory on the same organic interposer [9]. This allows the dissipation of energy to be reduced while moving data from/to memory, and the size of the communication busses to be increased. Together with a carefully designed memory infrastructure, the use of a multiplicity of coprocessors and processors with large L2 caches and wider micro-architecture, featuring an 8-wide decode block, Apple's high performance cores are currently by far the most widely commercialized design in the industry [8].

3D sequential

3D sequential, which consists of the wafer-level manufacturing of a low-temperature device layer on top of a standard Front-End-Of-Line, introduces the notion of very high density on the transistor-to-transistor interconnect, opening up a range of new architectures (sensor on top of CMOS, low-energy CMOS such as FDSOI on top of high performance FinFET devices etc..).

The alignment of the two layers is performed by lithography (rather than by bonding) which means a possible sub-10nm alignment accuracy between the layers.

The various 3D integrations outlined above are not at the same level of maturity. While wafer-to-wafer stack is already

Figure 14: Principle of 3D sequential integration (Source: CEA-LETI)

in production in a $\approx 5\mu\text{m}$ pitch for image sensors, other solutions may require a learning curve of five to 15 years depending on the technology. In addition to integration challenges, design and computer aided design (CAD) tools need some disruptive innovations in order to fully exploit such technologies.

To conclude, the evolution of transistor and 3D technologies is mandatory for the pursuit of solutions to computing's endless requirement for increasing performances (more compute, more memory and still higher efficiency). While the number of actors active in advanced node development is very limited (three are still in the race, TSMC being perhaps the only one in near future), heterogeneous integration will provide to end-users both the possibility of differentiation and another wave of innovation. Europe should find, or find again, an active role in this domain, leveraging its successes in the 3D arena.

References

- [1] Gordon Moore, "Cramming More Components onto Integrated Circuits," *Electronics Magazine* Vol. 38, No. 8 (April 19, 1965).
- [2] Gordon Moore, "Progress in Digital Integrated Electronics" *IEEE, IEDM Tech Digest* (1975) pp.11-13
- [3] D.E. Nikonov, I.A. Young, *IEEE Journal on Exploratory Solid-State Computational Devices and Circuits* 2015
- [4] Scotten Jones, "IEDM 2017 – LETI Gate-All-Around Stacked-Nanowires", *SemiWiki*, 12 Feb 2018, <https://www.semiwiki.com/forum/content/7282-iedm-2017-LETI-gate-all-around-stacked-nanowires.html>
- [5] Scotten Jones, "7nm, 5nm and 3nm Logic, current and projected processes", <https://www.semiwiki.com/forum/content/7544-7nm-5nm-3nm-logic-current-projected-processes.html>
- [6] https://zenodo.org/record/3947824#.X_TdU-DjJTY
- [7] <https://www.anandtech.com/show/14666/tsmc-3nm-euv-development-progress-going-well-early-customers-engaged>
- [8] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/3_nm_process
- [9] <https://www.anandtech.com/show/16226/apple-silicon-m1-a14-deep-dive>

Carlo Reita is a researcher at the Research and Technology Department of CEA (Alternative energies and Atomic Energy Commission), France and tasked with AI and Digital technology roadmapping.

Severine Cheramy is a researcher at the Research and Technology Department of CEA (Alternative energies and Atomic Energy Commission), France.

Marc Duranton is a researcher at the Research and Technology Department of CEA (Alternative energies and Atomic Energy Commission), France and the coordinator of the HiPEAC Vision 2021.

This document is part of the HiPEAC Vision available at hipeac.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2021.

Cite as: C. Reita, S. Cheramy and M. Duranton. Silicon technology is still in the game. In M. Duranton et al., editors, *HiPEAC Vision 2021*, pages 108-115, Jan 2021.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4719609

The HiPEAC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

© HiPEAC 2021